

TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATIONS TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract.

The article describes ways to improve the quality of education of English teachers in general secondary schools through the use of innovative methods.

Key words.

school, innovation, pedagogue-technologist, method, education, upbringing, knowledge, skill, creative, classification, innovation, objective.

Introduction

One of the most important conditions today is the introduction into practice of advanced pedagogical experience and achievements in education. Currently, a huge knowledge base has been formed that a teacher can use in the course of his activities, and every day it becomes richer. But, nevertheless, the assimilation of this experience by teachers and future professionals occurs with some difficulty. The position of a teacher is especially important in creating best practices and popularizing it among his colleagues. When introducing new advanced pedagogical experience into practice, the teacher should pay attention to its value, as well as to how effective it is. The innovative orientation of the teacher's practical activity makes it possible to put into practice the achievements of theoretical pedagogical research. It is in order to popularize the results of such studies that it is necessary to present them to the general public. Such innovations can be brought to the attention of other representatives of pedagogy by providing quick consultations by industry professionals, conducting special seminars and trainings, speaking at conferences, as well as links to a series of lectures for future teachers .

Here the question arises: "who is the carrier and propagandist of advanced pedagogical ideas and technologies to the general public?". When studying and popularizing the experience of an individual teacher or an educational institution,

the teaching staff of higher educational institutions, mature teachers who carry out activities in educational institutions, become important in this process. The reason for this can be explained as follows:

- the author of the innovation cannot give the necessary and accurate assessment of the prospects of a particular pedagogical idea or innovation;
- advanced teachers do not always think about popularizing their ideas. The reason is that novelty requires additional time, the work of a teacher;
- the idea is not always scientifically and methodically justified by its creator;
- authors face obstacles related to the individual characteristics of themselves and their colleagues when they present their innovations and ways to put them into practice;
- not only the promotion and popularization of pedagogical innovations, but also making adjustments to the competence of teachers based on them, the task of enriching the professional knowledge and skills of future teachers is assigned to the creative group;
- members of the creative team are also responsible for the systematic selection of innovations, monitoring, evaluation of innovative ideas, technologies, and enriching the experience of higher educational institutions.

The author of the innovative idea does not participate in the management of activities focused on practical application. This approach creates the basis for expanding the capabilities of an innovative teacher and orienting him to a specific goal. Thus, the forces of the founder and popularizer of innovative pedagogy are concentrated at one point and directed towards a specific goal. Pedagogical innovations have their own specific dimensions. Pedagogical innovations are considered to consist of the following indicators that form the creative activity of a future teacher: how new are innovative methods; how optimal they are; how effective they are; the possibility of using them in a mass experiment, and so on. The main dimension of innovative methods lies in their novelty, equality of research results and advanced pedagogical experience. For this reason, by carrying out activities in the innovation process,

It is believed that it is important for teachers who want to learn to understand what the true nature of innovation is.

Although the experiment being conducted is new for one teacher, this method may not be new for another. Moreover, the degree of novelty of the same method for future teachers may be different. Taking this into account, both future teachers

and teachers working in the education system will have to approach innovative creative activity based on their own needs

Innovative methods that contribute to the development of creative functions of future teachers, according to the degree of their novelty, manifest themselves in several forms: absolute level; local-absolute level; conditional level; subjective level. The mass application of innovative pedagogical innovations in practice is interpreted as a criterion for their evaluation. This is largely due to the technical security of the educational process and the specifics of the teacher's activity .

The creative application of pedagogical innovations in the mass pedagogical experience is manifested at the initial stage of the work of individual teachers. These innovations will be available for mass application after their experimentation and objective evaluation. It will be advisable to develop the creative functions of future teachers, using innovative methods that have gained wide popularity, have allowed to achieve positive results.

Diagnostic methods aimed at studying the innovative activity of a teacher are also diverse. The use of diagnostic methods demonstrates the strengths of the teacher's work. That is why arming future teachers with modern diagnostic techniques is a requirement of the time. Taking into account the professional needs and desires of future teachers, it is necessary to carry out full-fledged purposeful activities aimed at forming their professional and pedagogical ethics and its continuous development.

When studying pedagogical innovations based on diagnostics, one should not forget about the need to take into account that in the experience of each teacher, along with positive, developing circumstances, there are also negative manifestations. In order for a young teacher to work effectively in an educational institution, it is necessary to clearly indicate on the basis of diagnostics the positive and negative sides present in his work experience. Innovative it is necessary to clearly convey to the consciousness of future teachers that diagnostic methods used to study processes consist of:

- systematic study of pedagogical needs, interests, areas of special importance of future teachers in order to identify difficulties arising in the activities of teachers and the possibilities of overcoming them;

- search for and implementation into the practice of higher pedagogical education of ideas, concepts and advanced pedagogical experience that serve to meet their interests and needs;

-identification of the specifics and diversity of manifestations of pedagogical innovations among future teachers in the process of their development and application, the widespread use of such types of work as demonstration, illustration, conducting open lessons, working on new resources, organizing lectures, participating in experimental work. Practical work aimed at studying pedagogical innovations based on diagnostics is also advisable to be carried out in several stages. Conducting questionnaire surveys of future teachers at the initial stage, examination of the answers received to the questionnaire questions, organization of individual conversations and confirmation of information in the answers received to the questionnaire questions, analysis of the data obtained based on the results of diagnostics . At this stage, based on the results of the first stage, measures are planned aimed at improving the professional and pedagogical qualifications of the future teacher, as well as ways of their implementation are outlined. At this stage, the work performed is completed and repeated diagnostics is carried out. In this process, the future teacher focuses on obtaining intermediate and final results. The changes that have occurred in the activities of students in the group are deeply analyzed. As a result, the diagnosis of professional skills, skills and experience of future teachers and their equipment with diagnostic methods, as well as the restructuring of the process of vocational and pedagogical education based on innovative ideas allow students to effectively develop creative activity. As a result, it becomes possible to encourage future teachers to creative activity, to show initiative .

Creative pedagogical activity of a teacher is a process of positive solution of tasks subordinated to the formation of human consciousness, behavior, and most importantly-the creation of a generation of harmonious people. In addition, the developed learning goal is easily implemented, and the expected result is achieved faster. That is;

- it is necessary to clearly define the place and tasks of the teacher in the system of innovative educational technologies;
- the teacher must move to a new professional position-"teacher - technologist",- "teacher-technologist" ;
- the "teacher-technologist" must have special knowledge, skills, skills;
- it is necessary that specific measures be implemented to increase the authority, potential, moral, material interest of the "teacher-technologist" among the teaching staff.

In the development of the quality of education, effective results are certainly provided by the use of innovative technologies by teachers in the process of teaching in the classroom.

Conclusion

Summing up, we can say that for the education of mature specialists with a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, able to easily solve their tasks, our teachers today understand that the use of modern innovative pedagogical technologies is a key factor in improving the quality and effectiveness of education and upbringing, which takes time. must.

LITERATURE:

1. Artemov V.A. Psychology of teaching a foreign language. - M.: "Pedagogy", 1989.- p.103.
2. Bim I. L. Some actual problems of carpet training in foreign languages.- Yaish. 2001, No. 4.- p.39
3. Yoralieva U.Q. Features of teaching foreign languages in the preschool education system and the possibility of using interactive methods in it. Journal of Modern Education. -T., 2014, No. 9.-27 P.
4. Mansurov, N., & Jalilova, V. (2021). THE METHODOLOGY OF VOCATIONAL TRAINING IS A SCIENTIFIC BRANCH OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGY. Zbgrnik naukovix pras'S SCIENTIA. <https://ois.ukrlogos.in.ua/index.php/scientia/issue/view/26.03.2021/487>